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Advances on the optimization of the thermal treatment and modelization on the multi-stage wire drawing process with ZnAl15% alloy wires

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ABSTRACT

This study establishes a thermo-mechanical processing framework for design and optimization of the ZnAl15% multi-stage wire drawing by controlled heat treatment, constitutive behaviour modelling and analytical/finite element modelling (FEM). The work prioritizes (i) tuning pre-drawing microstructure for optimal ductility-strength balance, (ii) formulating a strain-rate dependent flow model incorporating DRV induced by partial recrystallization (DRX), and (iii) quantification of drawing load, friction, and temperature evolution to ensure process stability and dimensional integrity. Best alloy condition was achieved by heat treating at 233 °C (1 h ramp + 2 h hold + 24 h slow cooling), improving tensile strength and elongation capacity while maintaining ductility. The alloy exhibited mild strain-rate sensitivity ($m = 0.0225$, $K = 246.99$ MPa). During six drawing passes, DRV affected the mechanical response leading to elongation of the primary grains and an approximately 16% reduction in microhardness (from 62 to 52.2 HV_{0.3}). The yield strength and ultimate tensile strength decreased by about 18–20%, while the elongation at break was reduced by roughly 30–60%. These results indicate that the alloy undergoes work softening induced by the sequential forming process. The die/wire friction coefficient was established between $\mu = 0.18$ – 0.29 in the wire-die interface. Modelled drawing stresses agreed well with experiments showing < 6% deviation with respect validation experiment. Measured exit temperatures (26–36 °C) and predicted equilibrium values (45–61 °C at 1.27 mm from the die cone) confirmed consistent thermal behavior, while FEM revealed localized deformation-zone temperatures > 100 °C, sufficient to trigger DRV. ZnAl15% wire drawing can be robustly modelled integrating strain hardening and DRV effect due to work-softening (WS). The integrated methodology constitutes a reliable framework for industrial process design and optimization.

1. Introduction

The multi-stage wire drawing is a metalworking industrial process consisting of the reduction of the diameter of a wire by pulling it through a series of drawing dies of progressively smaller size increasing the wire's length while modifying its mechanical properties such as tensile strength due to cold plastic deformation. This technique is commonly used to process ferrous and non-ferrous metals and alloys such as those based on copper (electrical conductors), aluminum (electrical conductors, structures), nickel (aerospace and chemical applications requiring corrosion resistance), titanium (orthodontic applications), precious

metals (jewellery, microelectronics) and zinc alloys (anti-corrosion coatings applied by thermal spraying), among others.

One of the main applications of Zn-Al wire alloy (ZnAl2%, ZnAl4%, ZnAl15%, ZnAl22%, among others) is thermal spraying, a process in which the wire is melted and sprayed onto surfaces to create a protective coating. This technique is widely employed in industries such as marine, oil and gas, and infrastructure, where components are exposed to harsh environmental conditions. The Zn-Al coating acts as a strong barrier against corrosion combining the advantages of pure Zn (sacrificial protection as anode) and pure Al (passive protection) significantly extending the service life of the coated steels [1]. Thus, for thermal

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spraying, Zn-Al wire must combine good ductility and dimensional consistency to ensure correct spooling and feeding without cracking, maintaining sufficient tensile strength to resist the pulling forces of the feed system without stretching or breaking avoiding feeding interruptions or coatings with poor adhesion or inconsistent thickness.

To achieve the appropriate product quality in the drawing of Zn-Al alloy wires for thermal spraying, it is essential to focus on the quality melting and casting process of the raw initial rod (alloying elements, impurities and dissolved hydrogen control, homogeneity,... among others), but also on the appropriate design of the drawing sequence, as well as the stability and control of the conditions during the drawing process. Furthermore, central porosity and voids are a typical feature in continuously casting process of ZnAl15% rods for wire drawing purposes. Although process parameters in the casting line being built by Company Properzi (Continuus-Properzi spa, Milano, Italy) can be optimized to minimize this porosity, its complete elimination is difficult and hot rolling operations can reduce these defects significantly [2,3]. However, residual porosity may remain and act as stress concentrators during subsequent processing by cold deformation. Thus, this can notably affect elongation during tensile conditions that occur in the wire drawing process, as micro voids facilitate early necking or localized fracture and, as a result, wires from the same batch may exhibit similar ultimate tensile strength (UTS) but varying ductility levels. These effects are consistent with the solidification behavior and mechanical response of Zn-Al alloys, where microstructural defects play a critical role in tensile performance [4].

Another important aspect is the superplastic nature of this type of zinc-rich alloys, particularly reported in various previous works consulted [5,6]. In Zn-Al alloys, the low recrystallization temperature of zinc facilitates plastic deformation during conventional forming processes, since this alloy shows a particular grain-boundary sliding and rotation mechanism that facilitates its plastic deformation at relatively low temperatures with reduced flow stress [7]. This should not be confused with superplasticity, which refers to the ability of an alloy to undergo exceptionally large elongations under specific conditions. Thus, while a low recrystallization temperature enhances general ductility, superplasticity represents a distinct deformation phenomenon referred with the capacity of the alloy to undergo large deformations without localized necking leading to breakage [8]. In this sense, in the wire drawing process, localized necking must always be avoided, as it compromises material continuity and leads to fracture.

Although the industry is keen to automate and monitor the identification of processing conditions that could cause defects during wire drawing, currently, detecting problems during the process relies heavily on the experience and judgment of operators. Thus, previous work has been reported in which various process variable monitoring systems have been validated with the aim of detecting these problems and correcting them in real time. In this line, Pejryd et al. [9] investigated the potential of using vibration and drawing force monitoring to detect process variations that may lead to defects in carbon steel wires in different lubricating situations concluding that the system can detect loss of lubrication that leads to poor surface quality of the wire. Caso et al. [10] demonstrated a correlation of acoustic emission amplitude with lubrication conditions, die temperature or drawing speed, revealing the monitoring of this signal as promising to detect and anticipate problems in the process and in the quality of the drawn wire. Other consulted works proposed wire drawing force monitorization using direct measurement methods, such as strain-gauges attached to the die or load cells within the drawing machine, and indirect methods like monitoring the electric motor's power consumption. In this line, Larsson et al. employed four sensor signals—vibration, wire temperature, surface brightness, and drawing force—and showed that lubrication problems, reflected in an increased friction coefficient, could be detected through these signals. Their findings highlight the potential of sensor-based monitoring to identify process issues and enable corrective actions before permanent damage occurs to the wire or die [11].

However, these problems should be avoided with optimal process design, which relies strongly on reliable modelling. Analytical models have traditionally been used to predict drawing stress, drawing force, and temperature evolution, offering fast estimations but often with simplifying assumptions that limit their accuracy [12–15]. More recently, finite element modelling (FEM) has become a powerful tool to simulate the wire drawing process with higher fidelity, enabling the consideration of complex geometries, multi-pass operations, and non-linear material behavior. The reliability of such simulations depends greatly on accurate constitutive models of the wire material, since the prediction of drawing stress, strain hardening, and thermal responses is essential for anticipating process instability. Likewise, the tribological conditions at the wire-die interface play a decisive role, as friction and lubrication strongly affect drawing force, surface quality, and die wear. In this sense, the results of previous works have shown that a robust material behavior models combined with realistic friction laws are fundamental to ensure that process simulations provide trustworthy guidance for designing stable and defect-free drawing operations [16–18].

On the other hand, the strain rate sensitivity is an essential parameter in understanding the mechanical behavior of superplastic alloys such as Zn-Al alloy [19,20]. Previous research has been demonstrated that this type of alloy can be severely deformed by processes like extrusion or wire drawing at relatively low temperature thanks to the so-called dynamic recrystallization (DRX) phenomenon [7,21]. Thus, the previously mentioned material behavior model needs to implement this aspect for successful results both in analytical and numerical models of the wire-drawing process. In this sense, some recent works assessed the problem of ZnAl15% alloy and pure Zn wire drawing, but only from an experimental perspective [22,23]. Nevertheless, previous works that have been consulted validated a flow stress calculation model with implicit DRX kinetics in hot compression. Thus, Zhang et al. [24] defined a specific model to estimate the flow stress for AlMgSi alloy considering the strain hardening and dynamic recrystallization during hot compression that allowed them to build a numerical model for the evolutionary prediction of the microstructure and grain size of the alloy using numerical simulation obtaining good agreement between FEM simulations and experimental values also in hot extrusion process. In the same line, Mohammadi et al. [25] proposed the DRX model for ZnAl22% alloy that allows to predict the evolution of the flow stress during hot compression, observing that the activation energy decreases with the increasing temperature and decreasing strain rate demonstrating that, in the particular case of this alloy, dynamic recrystallization can thermally activated even at low temperatures. Nevertheless, the DRX model implemented in these works are governed by specific coefficients that obey hot working conditions.

The main objective of this study is to develop and validate a generalized thermo-mechanical modelling framework capable of predicting the coupled mechanical, thermal, and microstructural evolution during multi-stage wire drawing, with particular focus on strain-rate-sensitive and work-softening alloys such as Zn-Al, ensuring their applicability in thermal spraying applications. Therefore, the present work proposes a simple material behaviour model that implements both strain hardening plus softening effect that ZnAl15% alloy shows when processed by wire drawing, considering DRV dynamic recovery effect that occurs in this type of alloy and thus facilitating its integration in both analytical/numerical models. In this line, previous works demonstrated that hardness and yield strength of a ZnAl15% annealed alloy decreased continuously increasing cold rolling degree up to 80%, exhibiting work softening (WS) behavior due to the transformation of its structure constituted by Zn primary grains (η) and ($\eta + \alpha$) Zn-rich interlamellar colonies in equiaxed η and α grains by partial-DRX, whereas primary grains where only elongated along the rolling direction without any evidence of recrystallization [26]. A closer examination of the cold rolled ZnAl22% microstructure evolution revealed no evidence of primary grains refinement ruling out the possibility of DRX as the prime candidate for

WS behavior and demonstrating that a grain boundary-sensitive dynamic recovery effect (DRV) is responsible for the work softening behavior (WS) in Zn-Al alloy [27].

Thermal conditions of the wire drawing process are affected by several variables that are critical for the temperature distribution in both the wire and the die. A previous work by Hwang et al. [28] concluded that the maximum temperature (T_{\max}) of the die decreases with increasing contact heat transfer coefficient (h_c) between die-wire, whereas the wire temperature increases under the same condition. This behavior can be attributed to the enhanced transfer of frictional heat from the die to the wire as the heat transfer coefficient rises. In contrast, both die and wire temperatures decrease with increasing die thermal conductivity, since higher conductivity promotes more efficient dissipation of frictional heat into the die, thereby lowering the surface temperature of the wire in the contact region. Besides, temperature of both die and wire increases linearly with the friction factor, with the die temperature being more sensitive to variations in friction than that of the wire. Thus, optimization of these parameters is essential to minimize thermal damage, improve product quality, and extend die service life in industrial drawing operations. In this work, a numerical model was generated that allowed us to predict the temperature distribution and evolution in the wire during the wire drawing process. Previous works consulted have been developed analytical and numerical models for the calculation of wire temperature during the process. Wright defined a simplified analytical approach that has been implemented in previous research works that have been consulted [20,29]. This simple model allows to estimate the final, uniform temperature of a drawn wire fundamentally assuming that nearly all work per unit volume is instantaneously converted to heat within the wire. This temperature increase depends on the material's specific heat, and the model also calculates the thermal equilibrium distance required for the initial surface-to-core thermal gradient to fully dissipate. Also, previous research based on numerical simulation of temperature distribution in wire drawing determined an optimum drawing angle (2α) depending on the applied reduction (r) that optimizes the die wear and this directly related to a decrease in the wire temperature [30,31]. To this end, in the present work temperature values were experimentally measured and analytical and numerical models were developed to predict values for the wire temperature that affect the thermal behavior of the system.

In the present study, an optimized thermal treatment for ZnAl15% wire was defined at 233 °C for 2 h with slow cooling for 24 h, achieving a balanced combination of strength and ductility suitable for multi-stage wire drawing. Building on this, a constitutive material behavior model incorporating dynamic recovery (DRV) was developed to capture the strain-rate-dependent softening characteristic of this type of alloy resulting in a thermo-mechanical framework that integrates thermal treatment optimization with analytical and finite-element modelling of the wire drawing process. Besides, although ZnAl15% was intentionally selected as a challenging case study due to its pronounced thermo-mechanical sensitivity and low recrystallization temperature, which make it particularly susceptible to thermal softening and process instability, the proposed route is inherently material-agnostic and applicable to other metallic alloys processed by cold or warm drawing. Consequently, the modelling framework and optimization principles developed in this work are transferable to other cold forming applications and for other alloys with similar behavior, where accurate prediction of stresses, forces, temperature evolution, and process stability is critical for defect-free and energy-efficient manufacturing.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Supplied state of zinc-aluminum alloy wires

Zinacor S. A. (Grillo-Werke AG, Weseler Straße, Duisburg, Germany) has been supplied \varnothing 2.50 and \varnothing 3.17-millimeter wires according to UNE-EN ISO 14919:2015, in commercial format of 15–30 kg coils. Both

diameters were pre-processed by multi-stage wire drawing in origin, from 5.25-millimeter diameter wire rod obtained by Properzi continuous casting [3,32].

According to the supplier's quality certificate [33], the typical mechanical properties and chemical composition of the alloy are shown in Tables 1 and 2.

The as supplied wires have been characterized by uniaxial tensile tests following the standard UNE-EN ISO 6892-1:2020 [35] at a strain rate of 0.00025 s^{-1} in the yield region and continued at a crosshead speed of 12.5 mm/min (0.00208 s^{-1}) until fracture. As received ZnAl15% wires with a diameter of 2.50 mm exhibited a yield strength $\sigma_Y \approx 148\text{ MPa}$, ultimate tensile strength $\sigma_{UTS} \approx 178\text{ MPa}$, and elongation at break $e \approx 151\%$. The 3.17 mm diameter wires showed higher $\sigma_Y \approx 196\text{ MPa}$ and $\sigma_{UTS} \approx 215\text{ MPa}$, but a reduced capacity of elongation at break ($e \approx 34\%$).

It is known that both diameter wires were pre-processed by wire drawing and, eventually in the case of \varnothing 2.50 mm, the wire was thermally treated and hence their different mechanical tensile characteristics. Thus, the \varnothing 2.50 mm wire has a lower tensile strength since it is a final product made by wire drawing; however, its high elongation capacity suggests that it may have been heat treated after forming process to improve its tensile resistance for final application purposes. On the contrary, the lower elongation capacity at break of the \varnothing 3.17 mm wire suggests that it has not been thermally treatment after pre-processing by wire drawing.

2.2. Materials, equipment and procedures to define the optimum thermal treatment time and temperature

The definition of the optimal thermal treatment conditions to improve ZnAl15% alloy wires for the wire drawing process is crucial, especially the combination of temperature, holding time and cooling time. The present work includes a procedure consisting of a series of controlled isothermal heat treatment at two different temperatures (250 °C and 265 °C), followed by mechanical testing to assess the influence of treatment parameters on the tensile properties of the material. For each temperature, samples were subjected to holding times ranging from 1 to 5 h, and an untreated sample (0 h) was included as a reference. The cooling ramp has been established by slow cooling with the oven door closed for 24 h. All the samples consisted of ZnAl15% \varnothing 2.50 mm alloy wire specimens of 2 m length wound into a \varnothing 50 mm coil to facilitate its introduction and uniform heating in the Nabertherm model N 11/HR oven, with a maximum temperature of 1280 °C and a maximum power of 5.5 kW (Nabertherm GmbH, Lilienthal, Germany).

After thermal treatment, all prepared samples—including the untreated reference—were subjected to uniaxial tensile tests using ZwickRoell Pro-line universal testing machine with 5–100 kN force range and testing speeds from 0.0005 to 1500 mm/min (ZwickRoell, S. L., Sant Cugat del Vallés, Barcelona, Spain). Test specimens were prepared with a total length of 150 mm and a calibrated control length $L_0 = 100\text{ mm}$ (L_0) between reference marks. Tensile tests were conducted at two crosshead speeds after the elastic period, 12.5 mm/min (low) and 100 mm/min (high), and the speed in the elastic period has been configured in accordance with ISO 6892-1:2020 [35]. Each test has

Table 1
Typical mechanical/physical properties and tolerances of ZnAl15% alloy wires produced for thermal spraying according to supplier's material data sheet [33].

Properties	Value/range
Wire diameter, d [mm]	2.00–4.76
Minimum yield strength, $R_{p0.2}$ or σ_Y [MPa]	80–130
Minimum tensile strength, R_m or σ_{UTS} [MPa]	110–150
Minimum elongation at break, $e_{(100\text{ mm})}$ [%]	$\geq 50\%$
Density [g/cm ³]	5.73
Melting range [°C]	382–450
Diameter tolerance [mm]	+ 0.00 to –0.07

Table 2
Chemical composition of ZnAl15% alloy according to UNE-EN ISO 14919:2015 [34].

Element	Zn	Al	Others					Total others		
			Pb	Cd	Pb + Cd	Sn	Fe		Cu	Si
% weight (supplied state)	84–86	14–16	≤ 0.003	≤ 0.001	≤ 0.004	≤ 0.001	≤ 0.015	≤ 0.002	≤ 0.010	≤ 0.030
% weight (ISO 14919:2024)	84–86	14–16	≤ 0.007	≤ 0.004	≤ 0.011	≤ 0.001	≤ 0.020	≤ 0.010	≤ 0.012	≤ 0.170

been reiterated for three times, for a total of 36 tests for each treatment set point temperature as indicated in Table 3, obtaining mean values of yield strength ($R_{p0.2}$ or σ_Y), ultimate tensile stress (R_m or σ_{UTS}) and elongation at break ($e\%$).

A comprehensive understanding of the transformations in the ZnAl15% alloy can be achieved by analysing its solidification process in detail, which is elucidated through the phase diagram in Fig. 1 and the identification of the reactions occurring during cooling. Thus, it must be considered that the melting point of zinc and aluminum are at 420 °C and 660 °C, respectively.

As analyzed from previous works consulted [36–38], Zn-Al phase diagram exhibits a eutectic reaction at 382 °C and ≈ 95 wt% of Zn. At this temperature, the liquid phase L simultaneously transforms into two solid phases: an aluminium-rich solid solution β -ZnAl and a solid zinc phase η -Zn. Furthermore, a eutectoid reaction also occurs at 275 °C and 22.3 wt% Al (≈ 78 wt% Zn), where one solid solution (β -ZnAl) decomposes into two solid phases (α -ZnAl and η -Zn). However, observing the ZnAl15% alloy object of the present study, it is possible to deduce that a heat treatment in the temperature range 100–382 °C with adequate cooling ramp will allow the optimization of the metallographic structure and mechanical properties of the alloy with the aim of improving its suitability to be processed by wire drawing, avoiding unwanted elongation or/and wire breaks of the drawn product during the process.

Once this background information was reviewed, the optimum temperature for heat treatment of the wires used in the experiments was determined. For this, a set of isothermal heat treatments were planned at 100 °C, 150 °C, 200 °C, 233 °C, 266 °C, 300 °C, and 365 °C (see Table 4). These temperatures are pointed in the Zn-Al phase diagram (Fig. 1). Thus, each wire specimen was wound onto a mandrel of 50 mm in diameter to produce 1-meter length coils. Seven coils were prepared, one for each treatment temperature. The heat treatment consisted of a heating ramp of approximately 1 h to reach the target temperature, followed by a 2 h isothermal hold, and controlled cooling inside the closed oven to room temperature (≈ 24 °C) waiting for 24 h.

The mechanical properties of the heat-treated wires were assessed by uniaxial tensile testing. For each treatment temperature, three specimens (150 mm in length, with a gauge length of 100 mm) were cut from the thermally treated coil for testing according to the UNE-EN ISO 6892–1:2020 standard [35]. Tests were conducted following the procedure described in Section 2.1. The average values of yield strength ($R_{p0.2}$, σ_Y), ultimate tensile strength (R_m , σ_{UTS}), and elongation at break ($e\%$) were obtained for each treatment temperature, as well as for a reference specimen in the as-supplied (untreated) condition.

The optimized heat-treated condition for ZnAl15% alloy wires was identified as heating to 233 °C for 1 h, holding at this temperature for 2 h, followed by slow cooling to ambient temperature inside the closed

Table 3
Plan for the determination of the optimum treatment time for ZnAl15% alloy wires.

Set point temperature, T [°C]	Heating ramp time, t_h [h]	Set point time, t [h]	Cooling ramp time, t_c [h]	Tensile test speeds, v [mm/min]
250, 265	1	0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5	24 h	12.5, 100

oven over 24 h. This treatment stabilizes and optimizes the metallic structure for wire drawing, resulting in increased tensile strength compared with the as-received material while preserving a comparable plastic regime and high elongation at break.

2.3. Determination of the strain rate sensitivity by the velocity change method in the uniaxial tensile test

The classic hardening behavior of a strain rate sensitive alloy is described by Eq. 1 and depends on the evolution of the yield limit (σ_Y) during the forming process which, in this type of materials, generally increases with strain rate ($\dot{\epsilon}$), for a constant strain (ϵ) and temperature (T), depending on a strain rate dependent strength coefficient (K) and a strain rate sensitivity coefficient (m) which are characteristic of each alloy [20].

$$\sigma_Y = K \cdot (\dot{\epsilon})^m \Big|_{\epsilon, T} \quad (1)$$

To determine the strain rate sensitivity coefficient (m), uniaxial tensile tests were performed on ZnAl15% $\varnothing 3.17$ mm alloy wire specimens that have been thermally treated implementing the optimal conditions defined following the procedure described, a total length of 150 mm, and a gauge length of 100 mm. In accordance with UNE-EN ISO 6892–1:2020 [35], all specimens were initially loaded at a low strain rate of 0.00025 s⁻¹ up to the yield point to ensure consistent identification of the elastic-plastic transition, after which the target strain rate was applied throughout the plastic region until fracture. Then, tests were conducted at crosshead different speeds of 12.5, 25, 50, 75, and 100 mm/min in the plastic region, corresponding to strain rates of 0.00208, 0.00417, 0.00833, 0.01250, and 0.02500 s⁻¹, respectively, as defined by Eq. 2.

$$\dot{\epsilon} \text{ [s}^{-1}\text{]} = \frac{v \left[\frac{\text{mm}}{\text{min}} \right] \cdot \frac{1}{60} \left[\frac{\text{min}}{\text{s}} \right]}{L_0 \text{ [mm]}} \quad (2)$$

Fig. 2a represents the basis of the method used to obtain the value of the strain rate sensitivity coefficient (m) in the present study. In this context, Dieter [19] defined that the rate at which strain is applied to a specimen can have an important influence on the plastic behavior of the alloy. Thus, the exponent m can be obtained from the slope of a plot defined by the values of yield stresses obtained at different strain rates, as defined in Eq. 5. Therefore, the results obtained in these uniaxial tensile tests are summarized in Fig. 2b (data of these tensile tests are presented in Table 11). On the other hand, Table 5 summarizes the stress-strain rate coordinates, and the Eq. 5 allows to calculate the strain rate sensitivity coefficient (m), while $\dot{\epsilon}_{UTS}$ and $\dot{\epsilon}_Y$ denote the strain rates corresponding to σ_{UTS} and σ_Y , respectively.

Previous works consulted have been demonstrated that the ultimate tensile strength (R_m or σ_{UTS}) and conventional yield strength ($R_{p0.2}$ or σ_Y) are empirically correlated with the applied strain rate ($\dot{\epsilon}$) [19,39]. Then, when differences in σ_{UTS} and σ_Y arise primarily from variations in strain rate, such as those induced by different testing speeds in the plastic period. Therefore, it is possible to estimate the strain rate sensitivity exponent (m) by fitting the data obtained from tensile testing to Eq. 5, that has been derived from applying logarithms in the relationship between stresses and strains shown in Fig. 2a. Then, the strength coefficient (K) can be calculated by substituting the strain rate sensitivity coefficient (m), in Eq. 2.

Fig. 1. Phase diagram of the zinc-aluminum alloy and transformations on ZnAl15% alloy.

Table 4

Plan for the determination of the optimum treatment temperature for ZnAl15% alloy wires.

Set point temperature, T [°C]	Heating ramp time, t _h [h]	Set point time, t [h]	Cooling ramp time, t _c [h]	Tensile test speed, v [mm/min]
100, 150, 200, 233, 266, 300, 365	1	2	24	12.5

$$\frac{\sigma_1}{\sigma_2} = \left[\frac{\dot{\epsilon}_2}{\dot{\epsilon}_1} \right]^m \quad (3)$$

$$\ln \left[\frac{\sigma_1}{\sigma_2} \right] = m \cdot \ln \left[\frac{\dot{\epsilon}_2}{\dot{\epsilon}_1} \right] \quad (4)$$

$$m = \frac{\ln \left[\frac{\sigma_1}{\sigma_2} \right]}{\ln \left[\frac{\dot{\epsilon}_1}{\dot{\epsilon}_2} \right]} = \frac{\ln \left[\frac{\sigma_{UTS}}{\sigma_Y} \right]}{\ln \left[\frac{\dot{\epsilon}_{UTS}}{\dot{\epsilon}_Y} \right]} \quad (5)$$

As shown in Fig. 2b, the yield stress point remains nearly constant, while the ultimate tensile stress slightly increases with rising strain rate in the plastic period. This occurs because, as the strain rate increases, the time available for the material to undergo deformation becomes progressively shorter, preventing the alloy from completing a full DRX. Thus, the work softening effect is reduced and work hardening, although limited, occurs during the subsequent deformation processing stages.

If a multi-stage wire drawing process begins with the alloy having

mechanical properties with an equilibrium between a maximum tensile resistance and ductility, the first forming stages of the process can partially activate partial-DRX, and the material softens up to a certain point where the hardening effect can be neutralized due to the DRV effect. In this line, from this point on and in later passes applied in the wire drawing sequence analysed in the present work, the drawn wire maintained or even slightly increased its ductility, which has been reflected in an increment of elongation capacity at break and the value of its ultimate tensile stress limit, as can be consulted in the Fig. 7 of the Results section.

Therefore, since the classic strain hardening behavior model does not implement this dynamic softening effect, the present work proposes the incorporation of a softening coefficient (ψ) that is induced by the dynamic recovery effect (DRV) of the alloy during the cold forming process, expressed in Eq. 7. Thus, the hardening behavior can be expressed by Eq. 6.

Table 5

Stress-strain rate coordinates in the speed change method and particularization when testing specimens at $\dot{\epsilon}_1 = 0.00025 \text{ s}^{-1}$ until yield point and variable strain rates ($\dot{\epsilon}_2$) in the plastic period.

Point	Speed change method		Tests at different speeds	
	Stress coordinate	Strain rate coordinate	Stress coordinate	Strain rate coordinate
1	σ_1	$\dot{\epsilon}_1$	σ_{UTS}	$\dot{\epsilon}_{UTS}$
2	σ_2	$\dot{\epsilon}_2$	σ_Y	$\dot{\epsilon}_Y$

Fig. 2. Speed change testing method: a) according to strain-rate change in the tensile test edited from Dieter [19] and b) from tensile tests made with different strain-rates in the plastic period of ZnAl15% Ø3.17 mm alloy wires thermally treated with the optimized heat-treated condition (233 °C for 2 h and cooled slowly into the oven for 24 h).

$$\sigma_{Y(i)} = K \cdot \dot{\epsilon}_{(i)}^m - \psi_{(i)} \quad (6)$$

$$\psi_{(i)} = [K - \sigma_{Y(i-1)} \cdot (1 - r_{(i)})] \quad (7)$$

In this equation, the softening coefficient ($\psi_{(i)}$) in a drawing stage (i) depends on the strength coefficient of the alloy (K), the yield limit of the input material ($\sigma_{Y(i-1)}$) and the applied reduction ratio ($r_{(i)}$). If we consider the conditions in the deformation zone inside the drawing die, the average value of the yield stress ($\bar{\sigma}_{Y(i)}$) of the alloy when it is passing through the deformation zone and is being transformed inside the die would be expressed according to Eq. 8 in which the work hardening is expressed by the integer between current (i) and (i-1) previous deformation states and the work softening factor (ψ) is function of the average yield stress in the previous stage ($\bar{\sigma}_{Y(i-1)}$).

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{\sigma}_{Y(i)} &= \int_{\dot{\epsilon}_{(i-1)}}^{\dot{\epsilon}_{(i)}} K \cdot \dot{\epsilon}_{(i)}^m - \psi_{(i)} \\ &= \frac{1}{\dot{\epsilon}_{(i)} - \dot{\epsilon}_{(i-1)}} \cdot \left[\frac{K \cdot \dot{\epsilon}_{(i)}^{(m+1)}}{m+1} - \frac{K \cdot \dot{\epsilon}_{(i-1)}^{(m+1)}}{m+1} \right] - \psi_{(i)} \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

It must be noted that the softening coefficient (ψ) should be interpreted as a constitutive integration of DRV-induced work softening at the macroscopic scale, rather than as a microstructure-based DRX kinetics parameter, and Eq. 8 allows the analytical implementation of the evolution of the yield strength of the alloy transformed during the drawing process considering this work softening effect.

2.4. Experimental procedure, equipment and setup

The wire drawing sequence was conducted in a vertical milling machine model Lagun FTV-1 (Lagun Machinery, S.L.U., Legutiano, Spain) adapted for this purpose as shown in Fig. 3.

For this purpose, a pulling spool (1) was machined from EN-AW 6061 aluminum and mounted on the spindle, which operated at the desired rotational speed to provide the drawing force (F_d). The spool was aligned to ensure that the wire remained horizontal relative to the machine table and the die. During operation, the milling machine's vertical handwheel (Z) was gradually lowered, allowing uniform winding of the

drawn wire onto the spool.

The die box (2) consisted of a rectangular block of EN-AW 5054 aluminum with two functional cavities with enough space to contain the die and load cell and sufficient depth to accommodate a water-oil emulsion for lubrication. The rear section was designed to house drawing dies of larger dimensions up to $\varnothing 43 \times 45$ mm dies and the back section has been designed to accommodate little dies with $\varnothing 28$ mm and 15 mm height, in addition to the load cell. The die box has been clamped in a bench-vice fixed to the milling machine table and properly aligned with the pulling spool. At the starting point of the sequence, the wire specimen, previously wound and subjected to heat treatment in a laboratory oven, must be rolled up on a free feeding spool (3) equipped with a crank handle.

The drawing dies supplied by Frasan, S. L. (Frasan, S. L., Miranda de Ebro, Spain) are housed in a steel body with $\varnothing 28 \times 15$ mm and, with a carbide tungsten core, have been designed with a reduction angle $2\alpha = 13^\circ$. The dies set was constituted in six dies/stages following the sequence of output diameters: $\varnothing 3.17$ mm (thermally treated wire) $\rightarrow \varnothing 2.929$ mm $\rightarrow \varnothing 2.692$ mm $\rightarrow \varnothing 2.474$ mm $\rightarrow \varnothing 2.274$ mm $\rightarrow \varnothing 2.090$ mm $\rightarrow \varnothing 1.940$ mm. The bearing length has been established as 25% of the output diameter. All the wiredrawing sequence has been performed using Besal 35 emulsifiable oil (8–10% oil + water) with a density of 1000 kg/m^3 at 15°C with great cooling efficiency (Brugarolas, S. A., Rubí, Spain).

Each drawing die was slotted transversally on the exit face to accommodate a precision film-type NTC thermistor (MF55 series, Nanjing Shiheng Electronics Co., Ltd., Nanjing City, Jiangsu, China) to measure the die temperature at the die exit face (T_D). An additional thermistor was used to measure the wire temperature at the outlet of the die box (T_W). Both thermistors were calibrated against a PT100 platinum resistance thermometer (DIN Class A accuracy, $\pm 0.15^\circ \text{C} + 0.002 \times |T|$), which served as the reference sensor. Calibration was carried out at two fixed points— 0°C (ice-water bath) and 100°C (boiling water)—by simultaneously exposing the thermistors and the PT100 sensor to identical thermal conditions. The thermistor outputs at these reference temperatures were used to construct calibration curves, ensuring accurate and traceable temperature measurements throughout the experiments. The maximum calibration uncertainty was estimated to be within

Fig. 3. Images and schematic 3D representation of experimental wire drawing setup: (1) pulling spool, (2) die box (die, load cell and emulsion) and (3) feeding spool with crank handle.

±0.2–0.3 °C. Temperature vs. time data were recorded using the Arduino IDE software (version 1.8.19; Arduino [23]). The maximum temperature reached in the wire at the exit of the drawing box (T_W (CAM)) was additionally measured using a FLIR One Pro thermal camera (Tel-edyne FLIR LLC, Oregon, USA), compatible with Android devices. This infrared camera features a measurement range up to 400 °C, a thermal sensitivity of 70 mK, and a factory calibration indicates a maximum error of ±3 °C (or ±5% of the temperature difference between ambient and scene) under standard operating conditions—specifically, after at least 60 s of operation, with ambient temperature between 15 °C and 35 °C, and object temperature between 5 °C and 120 °C.

Prior to each pass/reduction in the wire drawing experiment, the thermally treated wire specimens (initially with 3 m in length, Ø 3.17 mm) were pointed by a grinding wheel. Using a special die holder, the wire was then pre-drawn through the die for approximately 30 cm to ensure sufficient length for engagement with the drawing machine. After setting up on the drawing apparatus, the specimen passed through the die and load cell, mounting both thermistors in position and wounding the wire twice around the traction spool to initiate the test. A Lorenz K-14 load cell (0.05–100 kN, stainless steel, IP60), with overall dimensions of Ø 30 × 9.4 mm and a central Ø 5.4 mm hole for wire passage (Lorenz Messtechnik GmbH, Alfdorf, Germany) has been mounted behind the die exit face to measure the drawing force (F_d). This load cell was connected to a Lorenz LCV model signal conditioning interface via USB and force data was recorded in real time by VS3 Lorenz software.

Geometric and technological parameters of the wire drawing sequence subject of this study are described in Table 6 and Fig. 4 shows the die setup with load cell and thermistors.

It should be noted that the linear drawing speed (v) must be converted into the corresponding spindle rotational speed (RPM), considering the pulling spool radius (R) in Eq. 9.

$$v = \frac{2\pi \cdot \text{RPM} \cdot R}{60} \rightarrow \text{RPM} = \frac{v \cdot 60}{2\pi \cdot R} \quad (9)$$

The drawing force (F_d) and temperatures (T_D , T_W and T_W (CAM)) were recorded in each reduction step/pass of the multi-stage wire drawing experimental sequence object of study. For this, three specimens of ZnAl15% Ø3.17 mm wire with 3-meter length underwent thermal treatment with the optimized heat-treated condition that has been defined. The multi-stage wire drawing experiment was repeated three times to obtain mean values of drawing force and temperatures.

2.5. Calibration: determination of the coefficient of friction (μ) in the wire-die interface

The coefficient of friction (μ) in wire drawing of ductile alloys depends strongly on lubricant performance, material characteristics, and processing conditions and direct experimental measurement of the friction coefficient at the wire-die interface remains challenging. Wis-treich et al. [40,41] proposed a split-die technique in which the separation force between die segments and the drawing force are measured to evaluate friction shear stress. Instead of a solid ring, the die consisted

of two segments held together and allowed to "float" against a radial force-measuring transducer measuring both forces simultaneously during the drawing process. The geometric relationship between the internal pressure and the resulting forces can be resolved to define the friction coefficient (μ) as a function of the ratio between the drawing force and the splitting force. Although this method facilitates the collection of real-time data under wire drawing conditions, is extremely difficult to implement and highly sensitive to misalignments that difficult to maintain a perfectly conical geometry under heavy loads. This is why Wright [20] suggested estimating the friction coefficient by rearranging the simple form of the drawing stress equation that directly considers the effect of measured drawing force and yield limit of the drawn material, as shown in Eq. 10.

$$\sigma_d = \sigma_Y \cdot [(3.2/\Delta) + 0.9] \cdot (\alpha + \mu) \rightarrow \mu_{(i)} = \left(\frac{\sigma_{d(i)}}{\sigma_{Y(i)}} \right) \cdot \frac{1}{[3.2/\Delta_{(i)} + 0.9]} - \alpha \quad (10)$$

It must be noted that a previous research work has been found that has determined values for the coefficient of friction between ZnAl15% or pure Zn under dynamic conditions (sliding) in contact with carbide tungsten (WC), and compatible with the tribological conditions that occur in the wire drawing process. Nevertheless, some technical data sheets and websites consulted give values between 0.21 and 0.85 for the static friction coefficient between pure zinc and mild steel, suggesting lower values for this coefficient, around 0.20, for sliding conditions between Zn and tungsten carbide (WC). In this regard, previous research by Popoola et al. [42] determined the coefficient of friction between WC and a steel coated with pure Zn, obtaining values around 0.13 under sliding conditions. This confirms that it is feasible to establish a minimum coefficient of around 0.10 under ideal sliding conditions between pure Zn or a high-Zn alloy in contact with WC. On the other hand, the previous work carried out by del Rey et al. [43] determined a maximum average value between $\mu = 0.25$ and 0.33 under specific sliding conditions in a low-speed drawing with near-dry lubrication of the ZnAl15% alloy with WC dies.

For this work, the friction coefficient of ZnAl15% alloy (wire) in contact with WC (die) has been determined measuring drawing force by the simple experimental setup proposed by del Rey et al. [43]. For this, 150 mm length Ø2.50 mm ZnAl15% alloy wire specimens subjected to the optimized heat-treated conditions have been used. The drawing force was measured across five consecutive reductions using tungsten carbide (WC) dies with a semi-die angle of $\alpha = 15^\circ$ and $\approx 8\%$ reduction (r). The tests were performed using a simple die holder device fixed on the upper claw of the uniaxial tensile testing machine. The tests consisted of a sequential multi-stage drawing of the wire specimen from its initial diameter down to Ø2.00 mm in five passes, always at constant low speed $v = 0.003$ m/s and near-dry conditions. Obtained wires were subsequently subjected to tensile tests determining the yield limit after drawing. Values obtained by the Eq. 10 are summarized in Table 7.

As can be calculated, the average value of $\mu = 0.29 \pm 0.03$ has been calibrated and based on these results and background, the value of friction coefficient has been established with a minimum and maximum

Table 6 Multi-stage wire drawing sequence object of the present study with all the geometric features, production speeds and associated strain rates.

Die nr.	Input diameter, $d_{0(i)}$ [mm]	Output diameter, $d_{f(i)}$ [mm]	Die angle, 2α [rad]	Die shape factor, Δ	Input area, A_0 [mm ²]	Output area, A_f [mm ²]	Reduction ratio, r [%]	Wire elongation, E [%]	Unit strain, $\Delta\epsilon$ [acc.]	Drawing speed, v [m/s]	Strain rate, $\dot{\epsilon}$ [s ⁻¹]
1	3.170	2.929	0.11	2.86	7.89	6.74	14.63	17.13	0.157	0.140	0.0226
2	2.929	2.692	0.11	2.68	6.74	5.69	15.53	18.38	0.327	0.166	0.0293
3	2.692	2.474	0.11	2.68	5.69	4.81	15.54	18.40	0.495	0.197	0.0376
4	2.474	2.274	0.11	2.68	4.81	4.06	15.51	18.36	0.665	0.214	0.0449
5	2.274	2.090	0.11	2.68	4.06	3.43	15.53	18.38	0.833	0.233	0.0528
6	2.090	1.940	0.11	3.04	3.43	2.96	13.84	16.06	0.985	0.276	0.0664

Fig. 4. Setup detail of the die, load cell and thermistors into the die box: a) detail of the Lorenz k-14 load cell, b) 3D representation of the machine setup, c) real setup.

between $\mu = 0.10\text{--}0.29$ (equivalent ideal lubrication and dry lubrication conditions). These values are consistent with those obtained for other ductile alloys drawn with tungsten carbide (WC) dies under adequate lubrication, which also typically range between 0.1 and 0.3 [17,44,45].

Water-based synthetic and semi-synthetic lubricants are commonly employed in wire drawing of non-ferrous alloys due to their lubrication efficiency, cooling capacity, and chemical stability. In these tests, 1 cm³ of synthetic Multidraw AL WM oil (Zeller+Gemelin GmbH & Co. KG, Eislingen/Fils, Germany) with a kinematic viscosity of 110 mm²/s at 40 °C, was applied directly at the die entry cone using a syringe. This lubricant facilitates the passage of the wire through the die, but the low-speed process is compatible with near-dry conditions.

2.6. Analytical method for the determination of the drawing stress, force and power in the wire drawing process

Considering a multi-stage sequential drawing process where a given area reduction rate is applied at each stage/drawing pass (d_{0i} to d_{fi}), the drawing stress (σ_d) could be determined by Eq. 11. This expression comes from the slab method that models the plastic deformation zone of the wire within the drawing die by considering homogeneous deformation, frictional work, and the additional energy required to counteract inhomogeneous deformation arising from material distortion in the surface of the wire with respect to its core. Besides, the cylindrical bearing section (L_c) infers additional action because of friction by allowing a calibrated wire cross-section enhancing surface quality [13, 46,47].

$$\sigma_{d(i)} = \bar{\sigma}_{Y(i)} \cdot \frac{(1 + \beta)}{\beta} \left[1 - \left(\frac{d_{f(i)}}{d_{0(i)}} \right)^{2\beta} \right] \cdot \Phi_{(i)} + 0'1 \cdot \mu \cdot \frac{L_c(i)}{d_{f(i)}} \cdot \bar{\sigma}_{Y(i)} \quad (11)$$

being $\beta = \mu/\tan\alpha$ and $\bar{\sigma}_{Y(i)}$ the mean value of the yield stress of the input/output wire in stage (i).

The effective plastic deformation zone I in a conical die, characterized by the area reduction (r) and die semi-angle (α), is represented by the geometric shape factor (Δ), as given in Eq. 12. Conditions where $\Delta \geq 1$ are generally associated with large die angles or low reduction ratios [41,48]. The reduction ratio (r) and wire elongation (E) for each

drawing stage can be calculated using Eqs. 13 and 14, respectively. The influence of redundant work is accounted for by the inhomogeneity factor (Φ), expressed in explicit form in Eq. 15 as a function of the mean diameter (\bar{d}) and the contact length (L) within the die reduction cone. The unit strain per pass is defined by Eq. 16.

On the other hand, the true strain rate ($\dot{\epsilon}$) for a single pass in the wire drawing process can be calculated using Eq. 17, where d_0 and d_f are the input and output diameters, A_0 and A_f the corresponding cross-sectional areas, α the die semi-angle, and v_0 the input speed.

$$\Delta = \frac{\bar{d}}{L} = \frac{d_0 + d_f}{d_0 - d_f} \cdot \sin\alpha = \frac{\alpha}{r} \cdot \left[1 + \sqrt{1 - r} \right]^2 \quad (12)$$

$$r = \left(1 - \left(\frac{d_f}{d_0} \right)^2 \right) \cdot 100 \quad (13)$$

$$E = r/(1 - r) \quad (14)$$

$$\Phi = 0.8 + \Delta/4.4 \quad (15)$$

$$\epsilon = \ln(A_0/A_f) \quad (16)$$

$$\dot{\epsilon} = \frac{6 \cdot v_0 \cdot d_0^2 \cdot \tan\alpha}{(d_0^3 - d_f^3)} \cdot \epsilon \quad (17)$$

The drawing stress (σ_d) depends on the die semi-angle (α), the applied reduction (d_0 , d_f), and the length of the calibration zone (L_c), and is further influenced by friction at the wire-die interface (μ), and increases by inhomogeneous deformation of the wire (Φ) that increases substantially as shape factor of the die (Δ) increases [20,41]. In addition, drawing stress (σ_d) must exceed the alloy yield strength to enable plastic flow through the die, with strain hardening playing a decisive role in the analytical model expressed by Eq. 11.

Present work proposes the analytical model for the calculation of the drawing stress (Eq. 11) considering the material behavior model (Eq. 7) and the coefficient of friction (μ) determined by Eq. 10 from the results obtained in wire drawing experiments and tensile testing.

Table 7

Values for the coefficients of friction obtained in the sequential wire drawing tests at low-speed $v = 0.003$ m/s and near-dry condition.

Die nr.	Initial diameter, $d_{0(i)}$ [mm]	Final diameter, $d_{f(i)}$ [mm]	Die angle, 2α [rad]	Reduction ratio, r [%]	Drawing force, F_d [N]	Drawing stress, σ_d [MPa]	Yield stress, σ_Y [MPa]	Friction, μ
1	2.47	2.37	0.13	8.1	309	76.1	131.0	0.28
2	2.37	2.27	0.13	8.1	290	71.5	126.0	0.27
3	2.27	2.18	0.13	8.1	286	76.1	126.0	0.29
4	2.18	2.09	0.13	8.1	255	83.8	127.0	0.33
5	2.09	2.00	0.13	8.4	275	87.5	151.0	0.27

2.7. Analytical modelling of the wire temperature in the reduction zone: Wright's model

As is known and explained in previous works consulted [20,29,49], the work per unit volume during wire drawing (w), is largely converted into heat. Although a minor fraction may be stored as crystal defect energy (e.g., dislocations, vacancies) or dissipated through vibrations and inertial effects, these contributions are typically negligible. Consequently, this work is commonly assumed to be directly related to the drawing stress (σ_d) causing a thermal energy increase in the drawn wire and die. However, under steady-state industrial drawing conditions, die temperatures are sufficiently high that heat transfer from the wire to the die is minimal. Therefore, it is a valid approximation that nearly all drawing work per unit volume is converted into heat within the wire. As the wire exits the die, frictional heating produces a thermal gradient, with the surface being hotter than the core. This gradient dissipates rapidly, and the wire soon reaches an approximately uniform temperature, aside from minor variations due to convective surface cooling. The resulting equilibrated temperature can be estimated by Eq. 18, where T_0 is the room temperature ($T_0 = 20^\circ\text{C}$), σ_d is the drawing stress in MPa, C is the specific heat of ZnAl15% ($C = 0.464\text{ J/g}\cdot^\circ\text{C}$) and ρ is the density of ZnAl15% alloy ($\rho = 0.00573\text{ g/cm}^3$).

$$T_{\text{eq}} \approx T_0 + \frac{\sigma_d}{C \cdot \rho} \quad (18)$$

Besides, based on fundamental heat transfer considerations, the distance downstream from the die exit where the wire attains thermal equilibrium (L_{eq}), can be expressed as shown in Eq. 19, being v the drawing speed in mm/s, d_f is the output wire diameter in mm and κ_w is the thermal conductivity of the wire. The thermal equilibrium distance (L_{eq}) can be defined as the distance from the die exit at which a uniform temperature is maintained across the wire cross-section (T_{eq}), reached because of the deformation work applied during the process, assuming no heat losses, for a given alloy or metal.

$$L_{\text{eq}} = \frac{v \cdot C \cdot \rho \cdot d_f^2}{24 \cdot \kappa_w} \quad (19)$$

The thermal conductivity coefficient's (κ) variability stems from intrinsic material properties and external environmental factors such as material composition, density, temperature, among others, which can significantly alter heat transfer capabilities. In this sense, the thermal conductivity coefficient of ZnAl15% alloy is not readily available in general material databases, but it is expected that it must be lower than that of pure zinc (approximately $130\text{ W/m}\cdot^\circ\text{C}$) [28,50,51], and therefore $\kappa_w = 100\text{ W/m}\cdot^\circ\text{C}$ has been established for analytical calculations.

This classical model has allowed us to establish an estimate of the temperature at the thermal equilibrium length to compare this value against the temperature values obtained experimentally and against those obtained through numerical simulation.

2.8. Finite element simulation for the determination of the drawing stress, pulling force, required power and wire temperature in the multi-stage wire drawing process

Finite element simulations of the wire drawing process were performed using Deform 2D software (SFTC, Columbus, USA) [52]. The strain hardening behavior of the ZnAl15% wire has been implemented in the materials definition window and defined by Eq. 6 (derived from Eq. 2). The coefficient of friction that acts in the models wire-die interface has been determined as $\mu = 0.175$. Moreover, drawing die was defined as a perfectly rigid body and the wire as a perfectly plastic body in an axisymmetric configuration and initial mesh consisted of ≈ 3000 elements over a 20 mm segment of $\varnothing 3.17\text{ mm}$ (1.585 mm in radius). Node displacements along the symmetry axis were constrained in the drawing direction, and automatic remeshing was enabled throughout the

simulation. Wire motion was imposed by applying a constant linear drawing speed (v) to all nodes at the end of the axisymmetric portion of the modelled wire, while Coulomb friction was defined at the wire-die interface. Thus, the FEM model reproduced the complete multi-stage drawing sequence pass per pass and, for each pass, the deformed state of the wire from the preceding stage was used as input condition to simulate the accumulated deformation in the final product. Furthermore, FEM models enabled the analysis of wire temperature evolution and distribution during the drawing process. Experimental measurements of wire temperature were then compared with FEM results to identify and validate the thermal conditions occurring in the wire-die system.

The drawing dies used in this work mount a fine-grained tungsten carbide core with a grain size between 0.1 and $1\ \mu\text{m}$ and previous works consulted corroborated that the thermal conductivity coefficient of fine-grain tungsten carbide die is around $\kappa = 60\text{--}90\text{ W/m}\cdot^\circ\text{C}$ [28,53]. Thus, thermal conductivity coefficients of $\kappa_d = 80\text{ W/m}\cdot^\circ\text{C}$ and $\kappa_w = 100\text{ W/m}\cdot^\circ\text{C}$ were assigned to model the die material and the ZnAl15% wire, respectively, in FEM Deform 2D software pre-processor. It is noteworthy that contact heat transfer coefficient between tungsten carbide (WC) and solid zinc (Zn) depends on a complex interaction influenced by temperature, pressure, contact area, and many other factors, though direct experimental measurements for this specific condition are limited. Therefore, the contact heat transfer coefficient (h_c) in the wire-die interface has been established as $h_c = 1000\text{ W/m}^2\cdot^\circ\text{C}$ as reference value, since, according to the consulted sources [54,55], this coefficient could be in the range of thousands of $\text{W/m}^2\cdot^\circ\text{C}$ in metal-metal contact, being usual values from 1000 to 2000 $\text{W/m}^2\cdot^\circ\text{C}$ when aluminum alloys and tool steels are implied. Table 8 summarizes thermal properties, process parameter ranges and their effects on the wire temperature.

Once the wire-die system model and boundary conditions have been defined in the pre-processor of the FEM software, a database must be generated and the solver module executed to obtain the numerical solution. Then, the post-processor allows the process to be simulated and the output variables of interest to be analyzed. Finally, the drawing stress (σ_d), drawing force (F_d) and wire temperature distribution have been directly determined by simulation in the post-processing interface.

2.9. Analysis of the mechanical properties, microhardness and grain evolution of the drawn wire

Specimens were cut and then cold mounted in Buehler EpoThin (Buehler Ltd., Lake Bluff, IL, U. S. A.) two-component epoxy resin and allowed a curing time of 24 h. The specimens were positioned during mounting to prepare the cross-section and the longitudinal section at half the thickness of each wire. The specimens were first ground on a Buehler AutoMet 300 polisher using silicon carbide papers with grit sizes of 120, 400, and 1200. After the grinding stage was completed, the specimens were cleaned with alcohol and air-dried with cold air. During the polishing stage, Leco 810 Dsdisk Pol Felt Red $12 \times 0\text{ PSA}$ nap cloths (Leco Corp., St. Joseph, MI, U. S. A.) were used with diamond paste of 6,

Table 8

Influencing variable ranges in the wire temperature during the wire drawing process simulation with tungsten carbide drawing dies and ZnAl alloy wire.

Parameter	Effect on wire temperature, T_w
Contact heat transfer, h_c [$1\text{--}200\text{ W/m}^2\cdot^\circ\text{C}$]	$h_c \nearrow \rightarrow T_w \nearrow$
Die thermal conductivity, κ_d [$50\text{--}150\text{ W/m}^2\cdot^\circ\text{C}$]	$\kappa_d \nearrow \rightarrow T_w \searrow$
Wire thermal conductivity, κ_w [$100\text{--}130\text{ W/m}^2\cdot^\circ\text{C}$]	$\kappa_w \nearrow \rightarrow T_w \nearrow$
Friction coefficient, μ [$0.1\text{--}0.4$]	$\mu \nearrow \rightarrow T_w \nearrow$
Drawing speed, v [$0.14\text{--}0.3\text{ m/s}$]	$v \nearrow \rightarrow T_w \nearrow$
Contact length, L (depends on die geometry)	$L \nearrow \rightarrow T_w \nearrow$
Bearing length, L_c [$0.485\text{--}0.732\text{ mm}$]	$L_c \nearrow \rightarrow T_w \nearrow$

3, and 1 micrometer (μm), and alcohol was used as a lubricant/abrasive carrier. In each polishing stage, a force of 1.25 N per sample was applied for 3 min, with the specimen holder and the cloth plate rotating in the same direction. Finally, chemical etching was performed with a 6% sulfuric acid solution in an alcohol base for approximately 20 s. Microscopic observation was carried out using a Leica CTR4000 inverted metallurgical microscope (Leica Microsystems S. L. U., L'Hospitalet de Llobregat, Spain). The $\text{HV}_{0.3}$ Vickers microhardness was measured on the longitudinal section of each sample with a Leco LV700AT hardness tester. Five indentations were made with a separation of 2 mm between them.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Determination of optimal heat treatment conditions (time and temperature) for the wire drawing process

In this preliminary phase, thermal treatment time was first determined, followed by the identification of the temperature that provided the best tensile properties for subsequent wire drawing processing of the $\text{Ø} 2.50$ mm ZnAl15% alloy wire.

Heat treatment begins heating the wire in one hour until reaching a stable temperature (250°C and 265°C) holding it over a time range of 0–5 h to finish with a controlled slow-cooling ramp inside the oven closed during 24 h. Then, tensile properties have been determined from the stress strain curves obtained in the tensile tests. The tensile tests have been made with 150 mm length ($L_0 = 100$ mm) specimens of $\text{Ø} 2.50$ mm ZnAl15% alloy wire supplied by Zinacor S. A. (Grillo-Werke AG, Weseler Straße, Duisburg, Germany). The tests have been performed at 12.5 mm/min and 100 mm/min as shown in the results summarized in Table 9.

Fig. 5 evidence the optimal treatment time range to obtain higher values of the tensile properties between 1 and 4 h while over a longer holding period of 5 h the treated material decreases its tensile resistance.

Nevertheless, considering a balance between the energy consumption and the mechanical properties obtained (tensile strength), it was

Table 9

Values of yield strength (σ_Y) and ultimate tensile strength (σ_{UTS}) obtained from tensile tests conducted at 12.5 mm/min and 100 mm/min on $\text{Ø} 2.50$ mm heat-treated ZnAl15% alloy wire.

Temperature, T [$^\circ\text{C}$]	Holding time, t [h]	Testing speed, v [mm/min]	Yield stress, σ_Y [MPa]	Ultimate tensile stress, σ_{UTS} [MPa]
250	As supplied	12.5	151.7	174.9
	1		226.7	236.2
	2		236.1	242.5
	3		232.1	238.6
	4		233.4	237.8
	5		208.7	210.2
265	As supplied	12.5	145.0	166.4
	1		236.1	243.7
	2		237.2	245.7
	3		235.9	239.6
	4		234.1	238.3
	5		236.3	240.9
250	As supplied	100	147.3	213.2
	1		223.9	243.9
	2		232.3	243.9
	3		235.2	240.5
	4		230.8	244.0
	5		201.8	220.0
265	As supplied	100	156.0	207.7
	1		233.3	255.5
	2		233.6	254.6
	3		235.2	256.1
	4		236.0	257.1
	5		233.3	249.0

considered appropriate to implement a heat treatment with a 1-hour heating ramp until reaching the treatment temperature, maintaining the sample at this treatment temperature for 2 h, to finally cool the material slowly inside the closed oven in 24 h. This will result in a tensile-resistant material that will allow for a drawing process with a lower risk of unwanted permanent deformations and breakage at the exit of the drawing die.

Next, after analysing the temperature range and phase changes according to the alloy diagram (Fig. 1) and without getting close the melting point of Zn, a new set of wire specimens of $\text{Ø} 2.50$ mm ZnAl15% alloy supplied by Zinacor S.A. (Grillo-Werke AG, Weseler Straße, Duisburg, Germany) have been used applying the heat treatment cycle time previously established. In this case, temperatures from 100°C to 266°C (maintaining the $\alpha + \eta$ phases) and exceeding 275°C up to 365°C (transformation of the α phase into the β phase) were considered with the aim of determine the optimal temperature for the heat treatment of the alloy. Thus, the evolution of tensile properties as a function of heating temperature has been graphically represented in Fig. 6 and the results are shown in Table 10.

It is reasonable to deduce that, for a successful wire drawing process, it is best to use an alloy with good creep and tensile strength but retaining its plastic deformation capacity without necking. Thus, it was determined that thermal treatment enhances the alloy's suitability for the mechanical requirements of the wire drawing process. Ensuring sufficiently high yield strength and ultimate tensile strength is essential to prevent undesired deformations at the die exit, such as undersized wire diameters or even wire breakage during wire drawing process. However, this better mechanical tensile strength should not be detrimental to the alloy's ability to deform plastically since the low recrystallization temperature characteristic of this type of zinc-rich alloy facilitates plastic deformation.

As shown in Table 9 and Fig. 6, an increase in heat-treatment temperature led to a systematic rise in yield strength (σ_Y) and ultimate tensile strength (σ_{UTS}), with a progressive reduction in elongation at break (e). Within the $\alpha + \eta$ phase field, the highest tensile strength values are achieved at 266°C ($\sigma_Y \approx 217$ MPa and $\sigma_{\text{UTS}} \approx 232$ MPa). However, this condition shows a marked loss of ductility evidenced by a large loss of elongation capacity prior to breakage ($e \approx 54\%$). Such limited plastic capacity reduces the alloy's tolerance to local strain concentrations at the die entrance and exit, thereby increasing the probability of fracture or process instability during drawing.

By contrast, the heat-treated condition at 233°C offers a more balanced combination of mechanical properties. At this temperature, both yield strength and ultimate tensile strength are significantly improved relative to the as-supplied wire (approximately +16% in σ_Y and +23% in σ_{UTS}), while the elongation at break remains sufficiently high ($e \approx 79\%$) to sustain the plastic deformation required during drawing thus preventing unwanted breakage and deformation in the stretched wire. Moreover, the presence of a well-defined and relatively broad plastic regime, with an increase of about 20 MPa between σ_Y and σ_{UTS} , indicates stable eventual strain-hardening behavior and mitigates the risk of early localization. This balance between strength and ductility makes the 233°C treatment more suitable for reliable wire drawing than higher strength but less ductile conditions.

Definitely, the optimum thermal treatment for ZnAl15% alloy wires was identified as heating to 233°C for 1 h, holding at this temperature for 2 h, followed by slow cooling to ambient temperature inside the closed oven over 24 h. This condition represents an optimal compromise between mechanical performance, process reliability, and energy efficiency, making it the most appropriate heat-treatment condition for subsequent wire drawing defining the reference material state used for all subsequent experimental wire drawing, analytical, and FEM analyses.

Fig. 5. Graphical representation of yield stress (σ_Y) and ultimate tensile stress (σ_{UTS}), obtained from tensile tests conducted at $v = 12.5$ mm/min on thermally treated $\varnothing 2.50$ mm ZnAl15% alloy wires, for treatments at: a) 250 °C and b) 265 °C, over a holding time from 0 to 5 h.

Fig. 6. Evolution of tensile properties of $\varnothing 2.50$ mm wire at different thermal treatment temperatures (100, 150, 200, 233, 266, 300 and 365 °C). Specimens in supply state corresponds to “SS” coordinate.

Table 10

Results obtained in the tensile tests at 12.5 mm/min for yield stress (σ_Y), ultimate tensile stress (σ_{UTS}), and elongation ($e\%$) with $\varnothing 2.50$ mm ZnAl15% alloy wires treated at different temperatures (from 0 to 365° C) for 2 h and cooled slowly with the oven closed for 24 h.

Transformation phase	Temperature, T [°C]	Yield stress, σ_Y [MPa]	Ultimate tensile stress, σ_{UTS} [MPa]	Elongation, e [%]
$\alpha + \eta$	As supplied	148.0	178.0	151
	100	155.0	175.0	158
	150	159.3	185.7	134
	200	176.3	205.0	124
	233	192.3	212.3	79
	266	217.3	232.3	54
	300	204.3	210.7	67
$\beta + \eta$	365	183.7	206.0	58

Table 11

Values of coefficients m and K calculated from the results of the tensile tests with constant strain rate in the elastic period ($\dot{\epsilon}_1 = 0.00025$ s⁻¹) and variable strain rates ($\dot{\epsilon}_2$) in the plastic period for $\varnothing 3.17$ mm ZnAl15% alloy wire specimens thermally treated.

Testing speed, v [mm/min]	Strain rate, $\dot{\epsilon}_2$ [s ⁻¹]	Yield stress, σ_Y [MPa]	Ultimate tensile stress, σ_{UTS} [MPa]	Elongation at break, e [%]	m	K
12.5	0.00208	198	216.0	79	0.0411	278.28
25	0.00417	207	219.0	69	0.0200	244.41
50	0.00833	204	220.0	39	0.0160	237.51
75	0.01250	208	219.0	39	0.0181	237.12
150	0.02500	206	233.0	47	0.0172	237.62

3.2. Determination of the strain rate sensitivity model coefficients (K and m) in $\varnothing 3.17$ mm wires

The material behavior of the $\varnothing 3.17$ mm ZnAl15% alloy wire that have been thermally treated under optimal conditions (at 233 °C for two hours, followed by slow cooling within a closed furnace for 24 h) has been characterized and results from tensile tests are shown in Table 11.

Based on these results, the average value obtained for coefficients in all the strain rate range tested ($m = 0.0225 \pm 0.01$ and $K = 246.99 \pm 17.75$ MPa), define the material strain hardening behavior expressed by Eq. 20.

$$\sigma_Y = 246.99 \bullet \dot{\epsilon}^{0.0225} \tag{20}$$

Comparison of the as received and thermally treated samples (when subjected to tensile tests at $\dot{\epsilon}_1 = 0.00025$ s⁻¹ and $\dot{\epsilon}_2 = 0.00208$ s⁻¹) indicates that the thermal process had a negligible effect on the yield limit ($\sigma_Y \approx 196$ MPa to $\sigma_Y \approx 198$ MPa) and ultimate tensile stress $\sigma_{UTS} \approx 215$ MPa to $\sigma_{UTS} \approx 216$ MPa). However, a substantial increment

elongation at break increasing from 34% to 80%.

These results confirmed that the as-supplied mechanical response of ZnAl15% wires is mainly governed by their accumulated deformation history and applied treatments, which differs between wire diameters as a consequence of different industrial routes confirming that an accumulated deformation without an adequate thermal treatment reduced the elongation at break of the Ø 3.17 mm wire, justifying the suitability of the thermal treatment for its subsequent processing by wire drawing.

3.3. Final state of the drawn product after the experimental multi-stage wire drawing sequence object of study

Mechanical properties and microhardness measured in the wires after each drawing pass are shown in Table 12.

At this point, a multi-stage wire drawing process reducing the heat-treated wire from Ø 3.17 mm to Ø 1.94 mm in six passes has been evaluated. Each drawing pass employed an area reduction ratio of approximately 15%, with variable drawing speeds at each stage to achieve a final production speed of 0.276 m/s (progressively increasing from $v = 0.140$ m/s at the first die to 0.276 m/s after the final die). Fig. 7 shows the evolution of tensile properties of the first two and last two drawn wires, starting from Ø3.17 mm ZnAl15% wire thermally treated under defined heat-treatment conditions.

A comparison of the initial tensile properties of the wire in the optimally heat-treated condition with those measured after the multi-stage wire drawing, a decrease in tensile properties after sequential wire drawing has been evidenced. As can be seen, yield stress and ultimate limit stress practically maintained their value in the first pass while elongation at break increased from $e \approx 80\%$ to $\approx 90\%$ (orange in Fig. 7). At the end of the wire drawing process, yield and ultimate limit decreased $\approx 20\%$ with respect to initial values with thermal treatment, confirming work softening induced by the sequential forming process, but elongation also increased to $e \approx 100\%$. In the same way, Fig. 8 shows micrographs of the first and last three reductions. As shown in these micrographs, an initial transformation in primary grains was observed. This deformation and consequent elongation of the primary grains was much more accentuated from the 4th reduction onwards, especially after the last drawing pass.

As shown in Table 12, Vickers microhardness ($HV_{0.3}$) decreased as the applied reduction increased. While the starting heat-treated wire gave a value of 62.0 $HV_{0.3}$, the value decreased to 60.6 $HV_{0.3}$ after a first reduction from Ø 3.17 mm to Ø 2.93 mm while the microhardness fell to 52.2 $HV_{0.3}$ in the final Ø 1.94 mm drawn wire. Furthermore, the micrographs in Fig. 8 evidenced a main structure with the Zn (η) and Al-rich primary grains ($\eta + \alpha$), distinctly illustrating their profound evolution induced by the wire drawing process. As plastic deformation accumulates from the initial heat-treated state through the sixth pass, the original structure that was constituted by thicker, elongated primary grains has been progressively converted into a strongly fibrous and highly aligned morphology characterized by longer and thinner grains in parallel to the drawing axis, a transformation particularly evident in the longitudinal sections.

Table 12
Geometric parameters of the sequential wire drawing process object of study.

Die nr.	Wire diameter, $d_{0(i)}$ [mm]	Die angle, 2α [rad]	Reduction ratio, r [%]	Yield stress, $\sigma_{Y(i)}$ [MPa]	Ultimate tensile stress, $\sigma_{UTS(i)}$ [MPa]	Elongation at break, e [%]	Microhardness, [$HV_{0.3}$]
-	3.170	-	-	198.0	216.0	79	62.0 ± 0.3
1	2.929	0.11	14.63	190.0	213.0	91	60.6 ± 0.1
2	2.692	0.11	15.54	173.0	194.0	70	58.5 ± 0.3
3	2.474	0.11	15.51	167.0	186.0	84	56.8 ± 0.8
4	2.274	0.11	15.53	168.0	184.0	89	55.4 ± 0.3
5	2.090	0.11	15.53	164.0	182.0	96	53.5 ± 0.4
6	1.940	0.11	13.84	159.0	183.0	100	52.2 ± 0.5

This extreme elongation that affected the phase substructures, including aluminum, is typically associated with strain hardening, but data obtained in microhardness measurements and uniaxial tensile tests confirmed that no significant hardening has occurred in this specific alloy. Therefore, it can be explained that, during the wire drawing process, the recrystallization temperature of zinc is reached within the die's deformation zone and, consequently, the alloy undergoes partial-DRX in its Al-rich ($\eta + \alpha$) phase during the actual deformation. This has been translated into a decrease in microhardness of up to nearly 16% compared to the initial wire. Similarly to what has been demonstrated in recent studies that have been consulted, at most, limited local recrystallization may occur in Al-rich regions [26], and the experimentally measured decrease in microhardness and tensile strength indicates that the dominant softening mechanism is associated with an accelerated dynamic recovery effect (DRV) induced by partial-DRX, rather than full recrystallization.

These findings highlight the suitability of the current proposal for the implementation of an additional work softening factor (ψ) in the constitutive model that defines the strain sensitivity plus work softening sensitivity of the alloy, softening effect induced by the partial-DRX and dynamic recovery (DRV) caused in the forming process. Then, the proposed material behavior model that considers this combined effect has been expressed by Eq. 21.

$$\sigma_{Y(i)} = 246.99 \cdot \dot{\epsilon}_{(i)}^{0.0225} - \psi_{(i)} \quad (21)$$

Therefore, the analytical and numerical models used to calculate the drawing stress (σ_d) for each drawing reduction stage (i) in the multi-stage wire drawing process were based on a material behavior model defined by the average yield stress value ($\bar{\sigma}_{Y(i)}$) that can be determined by Eq. 22.

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{\sigma}_{Y(i)} &= \int_{\dot{\epsilon}_{(i-1)}}^{\dot{\epsilon}_{(i)}} 246.99 \cdot \dot{\epsilon}_{(i)}^{0.0225} - \psi_{(i)} \\ &= \frac{1}{\dot{\epsilon}_{(i)} - \dot{\epsilon}_{(i-1)}} \cdot \left[\frac{K \cdot \dot{\epsilon}_{(i)}^{(0.0225+1)}}{0.0225 + 1} - \frac{K \cdot \dot{\epsilon}_{(i-1)}^{(0.0225+1)}}{0.0225 + 1} \right] - [246.99 - \bar{\sigma}_{Y(i-1)}] \\ &\quad \cdot (1 - r_{(i)}) \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

3.4. Drawing force measurements and validation of the coefficient of friction in the wire-die interface in sequential wire drawing

The multi-stage wire drawing process from Ø 3.17 mm wire rod to Ø1.94 mm final wire has been assessed in 6 sequential drawing stages/dies with near 15% of area reduction ratio in each drawing pass and the process has been performed at variable speed in each drawing pass to get a final production speed of 0.276 m/s (from $v = 0.140$ m/s in the first die to 0.276 m/s as production speed after the last die). The geometric conditions defined by the reduction ratio (r), the reduction angle (2α), and the bearing length (L_c) yielded the results shown in Table 13.

Coefficient of friction (μ) for the process conditions implemented in the wire drawing sequence object of study was validated using Wrights

Fig. 7. Results obtained from the tensile tests (at $\dot{\epsilon}_1 = 0.00025 \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $\dot{\epsilon}_2 = 0.00208 \text{ s}^{-1}$) of the drawn specimens starting from Ø3.17 mm ZnAl15% alloy wire thermally treated.

Fig. 8. Micrographs of the transversal (up) and longitudinal (down) sections showing shape evolution of the primary grains during the sequential wire drawing process.

Eq. 10, considering the experimental values of the drawing stress and yield stress of the wires after each drawing pass in this sequential process. Consequently, the mean value obtained from the values of the

coefficient of friction of each of drawing reductions has been $\mu = 0.18 \pm 0.03$. This value has been implemented for the calculation of the drawing stress in the analytical model and in the FEM simulations

Table 13

Values of the coefficient of friction (μ) determined by Wright's equation (Eq. 10) from the experimental values of the yield stress and drawing stress in the sequential wire drawing process.

Die nr.	Initial diameter, d_0 (i) [mm]	Final diameter, d_f (i) [mm]	Die angle, 2α [rad]	Reduction ratio, r [%]	Yield stress, $\sigma_{Y(i)}$ [MPa]	Drawing force, F_d (i) [N]	Drawing stress, σ_d (i) [MPa]	Friction, $\mu(i)$
1	3.170	2.929	0.11	14.63	190.0	611.7	90.8	0.12
2	2.929	2.692	0.11	15.53	173.0	620.4	109.0	0.19
3	2.692	2.474	0.11	15.54	167.0	501.5	104.3	0.18
4	2.474	2.274	0.11	15.51	168.0	432.2	106.5	0.19
5	2.274	2.090	0.11	15.53	164.0	367.9	107.2	0.20
6	2.090	1.940	0.11	13.84	159.0	282.4	95.4	0.19

implemented by Deform 2D software.

3.5. Validation of wire drawing force, stress and required power determined by analytical and finite element models

The results of the drawing stress, drawing force and required power (σ_d , F_d and P) that have been obtained by the analytical, finite element simulation and experimental methods for the sequential wire drawing process object of study are summarized in Fig. 9. Table 14 shows the detailed technological data.

Complementarily, Fig. 10 shows graphical evidence of the wire drawing stress (σ_d) distribution obtained by simulation with Deform 2D FEM software for each of the six stages/passes of the sequential process object of this study.

As can be observed, the drawing stresses (σ_d) obtained from analytical calculations, FEM simulations, and experimental measurements exhibit strong overall agreement, with discrepancies generally below 6% across the six drawing passes. The principal exception occurs in the first pass, where deviations of up to approximately 16.6% are observed between predicted and experimental values. This discrepancy is multifactorial and is primarily associated with the combined effect of a lower area reduction in the first pass ($r \approx 14.6\%$) compared to subsequent passes ($r \approx 15.5\%$), together with the distinct initial microstructural state of the wire. In this regard, the mean value of the flow stress into the deformation zone (into the die) is implicit in the alloy's behaviour constitutive model and is directly affected by actual initial flow stress of the wire. Consequently, the actual initial flow stress value of the alloy also affects the work-softening term causing this discrepancy making this discrepancy even more noticeable at very low accumulated plastic strains.

The constitutive material model employed in both the analytical and FEM approaches was calibrated to represent the macroscopic flow behavior of the ZnAl15% alloy after plastic deformation, implicitly assuming a relatively homogeneous microstructure. In contrast, the initial wire entering the first drawing pass may present a heterogeneous microstructure characterized by primary Al-rich ($\eta + \alpha$) lamellar colonies [26]. During the first reduction, the relatively low imposed strain combined with localized transformation within these colonies promotes dynamic recovery (DRV) due to this partial-DRX, producing transient microstructural softening that lowers the effective flow stress. Thus, the drawing stress is overestimated in the first pass.

Following the first pass, the accumulated plastic strain was sufficient to homogenize the transformed microstructure, and the constitutive model becomes fully representative of the material response. The

predicted drawing stresses converge toward the experimentally measured values from the second pass onward. Likewise, the experimentally measured drawing forces consistently fall within the bounds defined by the analytical predictions corresponding to the calibrated friction coefficients. The mean friction coefficient identified for the industrial drawing sequence ($\mu \approx 0.18$) yields analytical and FEM predictions that closely match the experimental results, confirming that the combined frictional and constitutive descriptions accurately capture the wire-die interaction once stable drawing conditions are established.

3.6. Analysis of wire temperature during the wire drawing process

Table 15 shows the average temperature values obtained with thermistors (T_D and T_W) and the maximum temperature observed by thermal imaging ($T_{W(CAM)}$). Complementarily, the wire equilibrium temperature (T_{eq}) at the exit of the die has been predicted by both analytical model ($T_{W(ANA)}$) and FEM simulation ($T_{W(FEM)}$).

Comparing the experimentally measured wire and die temperatures with those predicted by analytical and FEM models for six drawing passes, the die temperature (T_D) remained nearly constant between 33 and 36 °C, indicating stable thermal conditions throughout the process. Wire temperatures measured with thermistors ($T_W \approx 26\text{--}29$ °C) and thermal imaging ($T_{W(CAM)} \approx 33\text{--}36$ °C) showed similar trends, with a gradual increase up to the fifth pass followed by a slight decrease.

It should be noted that the experimental measurements were taken at an average distance of $L_{meas} = 20$ mm from the exit of the reduction cone. In contrast, the equilibrium length ($L_{eq} = 1.27$ mm), defined as the distance from the die exit at which a uniform temperature distribution ($T_{eq} = T_{W(ANA)}$ at $L_{eq} = 1.27$ mm) is reached across the wire section under adiabatic conditions, represents the theoretical position where the deformation-induced heat is fully dissipated within the material. Therefore, the lower experimental temperatures compared with model predictions can be attributed partly to this measurement location, since heat losses to the environment and die cooling become significant beyond L_{eq} .

The manufacturer of the thermal camera specifies a maximum error of ± 3 °C under static measurement conditions. Consequently, the discrepancies observed between the thermal camera readings and the contact measurements (thermistors) can be attributed to the intrinsic accuracy limitations of the camera, as well as emissivity effects associated with the shiny surface of the wire and the fact that the material is in motion. In this sense, the thermal camera and thermistor measurements do not represent identical physical quantities. The thermal camera allowed to read an unstable value of the maximum surface temperature

Fig. 9. Comparative evolution of the modelled and experimental drawing stress (σ_d) when working with ZnAl15% alloy $\varnothing 3.17$ mm wire that has been thermally treated.

Table 14
Summary of the results of the technological outputs obtained in the wire drawing process.

Pass Nr.	Process model →						Analytical				FEM Simulation				Experimental			
	d_0 [mm]	d_f [mm]	v [m/s]	2α [°]	L_c [mm]	r [%]	$\Delta\epsilon$ (adim.)	σ_d [MPa]	F_d [N]	P [kW]	σ_d [MPa]	F_d [N]	P [kW]	σ_d [MPa]	F_d [N]	P [kW]		
1	3.170	2.929	0.140	13	0.732	14.63	0.1575	108.9	734.3	0.103	103.0	0.097	90.8	694.2	0.097	611.7	0.085	
2	2.929	2.692	0.166	13	0.673	15.53	0.3269	105.4	599.7	0.100	106.0	0.100	109.0	603.1	0.100	620.4	0.103	
3	2.692	2.474	0.197	13	0.619	15.54	0.4949	102.2	491.4	0.097	99.9	0.095	104.3	480.5	0.095	501.5	0.098	
4	2.474	2.274	0.214	13	0.569	15.51	0.6644	99.1	402.3	0.086	96.4	0.084	106.5	391.4	0.084	432.2	0.092	
5	2.274	2.090	0.233	13	0.523	15.53	0.8330	97.2	333.5	0.078	93.1	0.074	107.2	319.3	0.074	367.9	0.085	
6	2.090	1.940	0.276	13	0.485	13.84	0.9804	93.9	277.8	0.077	86.7	0.071	95.4	256.6	0.071	282.4	0.0779	
									ΣP	0.540			0.521	ΣP		0.544		

within the interest zone, whereas the thermistor measured the local wire temperature in direct contact with the wire at a fixed position with greater stability and significantly lower uncertainty. Consequently, infrared measurements are inherently associated with a higher value. Besides, the thermistor, being in direct contact with the wire, is largely insensitive to emissivity, reflectivity, and ambient radiation effects, while the thermal camera is affected by emissivity variations of the shiny surface, wire motion, and the difficulty of defining true peak temperatures under dynamic conditions. When these factors are considered, the observed differences between $T_{W(CAM)}$ and T_W were from approximately 18–34%, are consistent with the combined effects of peak-versus-local temperature measurement, the intrinsic camera accuracy (± 3 °C under static conditions), and additional uncertainty due to surface reflectivity and wire motion. These discrepancies therefore reflect the fundamental different characteristics of the two measurement techniques.

Fig. 11 presents result of instantaneous temperature on the drawn wire at the die box exit measured by thermal imaging camera ($T_{W(CAM)}$) and Fig. 12 shows the temperature distribution along the drawn wire simulated by FEM software and the equilibrium temperature ($T_{W(FEM)}$) picked at $L_{eq} = 1.27$ mm.

The analytical model ($T_{W(ANA)}$ at $L_{eq.} = 1.27$ mm) predicted higher wire equilibrium temperatures (54–61 °C) than those measured experimentally, likely due to the assumption of adiabatic conditions and simplified heat transfer boundary conditions. Besides, FEM simulations provided two temperature sets: $T_{W(FEM)}$ at $L_{meas.} = 20$ mm between 21 and 23 °C out of the die exit, and $T_{W(FEM)}$ at $L_{eq.} = 1.27$ mm between 45 and 50 °C at the equilibrium section. The latter values agreed more closely with the analytical results, confirming the consistency between both modelling approaches and their ability to represent the thermal field near equilibrium section of the drawn wire.

Overall, experimental temperatures were systematically lower than those predicted by the models, primarily due to measurement position and real heat losses not accounted for in the analytical or FEM formulations. Nevertheless, both modelling methods successfully reproduced the general temperature evolution across drawing passes, supporting their reliability for estimating the wire’s thermal behavior during drawing. As shown in simulations, FEM results have shown that temperatures near 100 °C and above develop within the deformation zone, enabling dynamic recrystallization of ZnAl15% alloy even under cold forming conditions at room temperature. Besides, the results predicted in the simulation are in correspondence with those analytically calculated, although simulated temperatures ($T_{W(FEM)}$) at equilibrium distance have been between 10% and 20% lower than those analytically predicted ($T_{W(ANA)}$).

4. Conclusions

The conclusions of this study demonstrate that ZnAl15% wire drawing can be accurately described using a constitutive model that couples strain hardening with dynamic recrystallization softening, achieving strong agreement between analytical, FEM, and experimental data, with drawing stress deviations generally below 6% across the wire drawing sequence object of study and consistent thermal predictions validated by direct temperature measurements. The application of a 233 °C / 2 h heat treatment with controlled slow cooling (optimized heat-treated condition) further confirms that an optimized initial microstructure enables the simultaneous attainment of appropriate tensile resistance and ductility for wire drawing.

The main conclusions of the results obtained in the present work can be summarized as follows:

- The differences between the \emptyset 3.17 mm and \emptyset 2.50 mm ZnAl15% wires in the as-supplied condition derive from their distinct histories. Consequently, despite identical composition, the wires exhibit different initial mechanical properties. The higher elongation

Fig. 10. Drawing stress (σ_d) distributions simulated by FEM software for each of the six drawing passes of the wire drawing sequence object of study: a) \varnothing 3.17 to \varnothing 2.929 mm \rightarrow f) \varnothing 2.09 to \varnothing 1.94 mm.

Table 15
Wire temperatures obtained experimentally and by modelling the wire drawing process.

Die nr.	d_0 (i) [mm]	d_f (i) [mm]	Process experiments			Process models				
			Die temp., T_D [°C]	Internal thermistor	External thermistor	Thermal camera	Analytical (Wright)		FEM Simulations	
							Wire temp. ¹ , T_W [°C]	Wire max. temp. ¹ , T_W (CAM) [°C]	Wire temp. ² , T_W (ANA) [°C]	Wire temp. ¹ , T_W (FEM) [°C]
1	3.170	2.929	35.0	26.2	35.2	54.1	21.3	47.7		
2	2.929	2.692	35.7	29.0	35.7	61.0	23.4	49.5		
3	2.692	2.474	34.9	26.3	34.9	59.2	22.3	47.2		
4	2.474	2.274	33.4	28.3	33.3	60.0	21.5	45.2		
5	2.274	2.090	34.1	29.0	34.1	60.3	21.0	47.6		
6	2.090	1.940	34.4	27.6	34.4	55.8	21.0	49.8		

¹ Experimental measurements have been done at average distance of $L_{meas.} = 20$ mm from the exit of the reduction cone into the die.

² The equilibrium length (L_{eq}) has been determined as $L_{eq} = 1.27$ mm.

capacity of the \varnothing 2.50 mm wire ($e \approx 151\%$) suggests a pre-treatment in the supplied material for a more stable plastic deformation behavior and better suitability for its final application in thermal spraying. On the contrary, the notably lower elongation capacity of the as received \varnothing 3.17 mm wire ($e \approx 34\%$) suggests a history of a pre-process by wire drawing without subsequent heat treatment. This observation has motivated the definition of a thermal treatment with potential applicability to this alloy in other supply conditions, allowing to improve the drawability to continue a subsequent multi-stage wire drawing.

- Optimal heat-treatment schedule has been defined as 233 °C with 1 h heating ramp, 2 h hold, followed by 24 h slow cooling, providing the best balance between tensile strength and retained ductility for wire drawing (optimized heat-treated condition).

- The proposed thermal treatment effectively maintained the tensile strength and plasticity of the as received \varnothing 3.17 mm ZnAl15% alloy wire, increasing its capacity of elongation at break from approximately $e \approx 30\%$ to $e \approx 80\%$. This enhancement prevents premature failure and unwanted deformations during subsequent processing by wire drawing.
- Excessive holding time (5 h) degrades tensile strength, while 1–4 h maintain high strength, confirming time sensitivity of thermal exposure.
- Partial dynamic recrystallization (partial-DRX) occurred during drawing, causing material work softening induced by dynamic recovery effect (DRV). This fact has been evidenced by reductions in the microhardness ($\sim 16\%$, from 62 HV_{0.3} to 52.2 HV_{0.3}), yield limit

Fig. 11. Temperature distribution measured with the thermal camera in each of the six stages/passes during the sequential wire drawing process: a) Ø3.17 to Ø2.929 mm → f) Ø2.09 to Ø1.94 mm.

Fig. 12. Temperature distributions in the multi-stage wire drawing sequence: a) Ø 3.17 to Ø 2.929 mm → f) Ø 2.09 to Ø 1.94 mm (Equilibrium temperature (T_w (FEM)) picked at $L_{eq} = 1.27$ mm from the die cone).

- (~20%, from 198 MPa to 159 MPa) and ultimate tensile stress (~17.6%, from 222 MPa to 183 MPa) in the forming process.
- Plasticity has been partially restored during drawing, with elongation at break decreasing ~34% in the final drawn wire, despite reductions in yield limit and ultimate tensile stress limit, confirming

- work softening induced by DRV and partial-DRX rather than strain hardening.
- Strain-rate sensitivity coefficients were determined as $m = 0.0225$ and $K = 246.99$ MPa, and a work softening coefficient (ψ) that is function of the applied reduction ($r_{(i)}$) and the evolution of the yield

stress ($\sigma_{(i)}$) during the sequential forming process has been proposed, defining the constitutive behavior model of the alloy object of study.

- The values of drawing stress obtained by the proposed analytical and FEM models has thrown a deviation of $\sim 18\%$ in the first pass, but the errors were generally $< 6\%$ after the first pass confirming the good agreement with the experimental measurements. This can be due to the particular superplastic condition of the alloy wire just after thermal treatment and because of the lower area reduction applied in the first wire drawing pass, which has led to a greater divergence between models and experienced results in the drawing force in the first die.
- The mean friction coefficient at the die-wire interface has been experimentally predetermined in a calibration test in dry conditions at a low speed of $v = 0.003$ m/s being, $\mu = 0.29 \pm 0.03$. Subsequently, it has been experimentally validated in multi-stage wire drawing conditions (from $v = 0.140$ m/s in the first die to 0.276 m/s in the last die of a sequence of 6 passes with lubrication based on water-oil emulsion), obtaining $\mu = 0.18 \pm 0.03$.
- Thermal rise in the wire during drawing is moderate and stable: experimental temperatures ($26\text{--}36$ °C) and modelled equilibrium temperatures ($45\text{--}61$ °C) have shown discrepancies explained by measurement location and model assumptions (adiabatic vs. real heat loss). FEM and analytical thermal predictions correlated well at equilibrium length (1.27 mm from die exit).
- The combined experimental, analytical, and FEM framework reliably characterizes drawability of ZnAl15% alloy wire, enabling accurate prediction of drawing forces, stresses, power, friction, temperature, and microstructural evolution, while identifying the need to include a dynamic recrystallization softening term in future constitutive models.

The methodology implemented in this work, combining controlled heat treatment, tensile testing, strain-rate sensitive material modelling, friction characterization, and multi-stage wire drawing analytical calculations and FEM simulations validated by experiments, proved effective for evaluating and optimizing the processing of ZnAl15% alloy wire. However, the primary contribution of this work lied in the development and validation of a general thermo-mechanical framework for multi-stage wire drawing. The proposed modelling approach, which integrates thermal treatment optimization path, strain-rate-dependent and work softening material behavior, and coupled analytical and finite-element process models, is inherently material-independent and applicable to a wide range of alloys and forming conditions. ZnAl15% was deliberately selected as a challenging benchmark due to its strong thermo-mechanical sensitivity, enabling robust validation of both work-hardening and work-softening mechanisms. Consequently, the industrial relevance of this work derives from the transferability of the methodology, supporting process design and optimization, improved process robustness, reduced trial-and-error, and enhanced energy efficiency in industrial wire drawing and other forming applications.

Author contributions

Conceptualization, O. R. A. and J. C. dR.; data curation, J. C. R.; formal analysis, J. C. dR. and O. R. A.; investigation, J. C. dR.; methodology, J. C. dR.; project administration, G. G. V.; lab resources, O. R. A., F. C., F. T. and J. M. A.; supervision, G. G. V. and O. R. A.; validation, all authors.; writing - original draft, J. C. dR. writing - review and editing, J. C. dR., G. G. V. and O. R. A.

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José Manuel Artímez: Resources. **Rodríguez-Alabanda Oscar:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Software, Resources, Project administration, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **J.C. del Rey:**

Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **G. Guerrero-Vacas:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Conceptualization. **F. Comino:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Software, Resources, Formal analysis, Data curation. **F. Taboas:** Validation, Software, Resources, Data curation.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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